

Secure Power AR Automatic Adjustment

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Abstract:- You can alter your invoices, debit memos, chargebacks, on-account credits, deposits, and guarantees in Oracle Receivables either positively or negatively. modifications that are within your approval limits can be approved, while modifications that are outside of your approval limits can be given a pending status. Debit products that satisfy your criteria for selection can be automatically written off.

I. SCOPE

The scope of this design includes automatic/simplifying all AR adjustments created by users manually.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Globally AR business users identifying the transactions which needs to be closed with minimum outstanding manually then creating adjustment against those invoices manually. Once adjustments are created supervisor will review and approve it. This involves more manual work during month end.

III. DESIGN OVERVIEW

Fig 1 Design Overview

IV. PROCESS

➤ Identify the Transactions and Fill Details

Fig 2 Identify Transaction

➤ *Select Generate Report only and Click on Submit to Generate Report*

Fig 3 Submit and Generate Report

➤ *Report will be Triggered.*

Fig 4 View Report

➤ *Click on View Output*

Customer Name		Number	Invoice		Due Date	Adjustment Number	Adjusted Amount	Balance Due	Adjustment Status
			Number	Type					
IC_CN2201_SCHNEIDER ELECT		6391	50403288	Intercompany	21-JUL-21		(0.03)	0.00	Approved
			50403335	Intercompany	22-OCT-21		(0.02)	0.00	Approved
			50403359	Intercompany	18-DEC-21		(0.07)	0.00	Approved
			57052356	IC INV SHANGHA	22-OCT-17		(0.06)	0.00	Approved
IC_CN4000_SCHNEIDER ELECT		15660	50402546	Intercompany	25-APR-18		(0.03)	0.00	Approved
			55526992	DEBIT MEMO	27-DEC-14		(0.51)	0.00	Approved
			57083132	IC INV XIAMEN	30-JAN-20		(0.65)	0.00	Approved
			57083133	IC INV XIAMEN	30-JAN-20		(0.78)	0.00	Approved
			57101756	IC INV XIAMEN	08-SEP-21		(0.05)	0.00	Approved
IC_DK1500_SCHNEIDER ELECT		101330	50403015	Intercompany	25-APR-20		(0.27)	0.00	Approved
			50403122	Intercompany	25-NOV-20		(0.51)	0.00	Approved
			50403279	Intercompany	25-AUG-21		(0.01)	0.00	Approved
			50403333	Intercompany	25-DEC-21		(0.01)	0.00	Approved
IC_PH0600_APC PHILIPPINES		1074	50403363	Intercompany	18-DEC-21		(0.09)	0.00	Approved
			57102473	IC INV PHIL	01-OCT-21		(0.01)	0.00	Approved
			57102476	IC INV PHIL	01-OCT-21		(0.89)	0.00	Approved
IC_SG2400_SEIT SINGAPORE		43442	50403362	Intercompany	11-FEB-22		(0.16)	0.00	Approved
			67008796	IC INV SE SG D	20-MAR-18		(0.01)	0.00	Approved
Approved Adjustments Total:							(4.16)	0.00	
Approved Adjustments Count:							18		

Fig 5 Report Output

- *Report Output will Show the Invoice Details which all will be Adjusted by this Process.*

➤ *Change Option to Create Adjustments*

Fig 6 Create Adjustment

➤ Click on Submit

Fig 7 Submit Adjustment

V. OUTCOME

- Open invoices falling under filter criteria will be adjusted/closed automatically.
- If the adjustment amount is within approval limit of the user who is doing the process will not required to approve it again and if it is beyond the limit it will be sent for approval.

VI. CONCLUSION

Benefit: As discussed with business, approx. 100 adjustments will take around 3-4 hours, In a moth there will be 500+ adjustments, so overall time taken in a month to perform this activity manually around 15-20 hours If we use this automatic adjustment functionality, system will take 10-15 mins approximately for 100 CM's, likewise the program can be used at global level i.e., all other entities also can use it and impact will be high. Especially during month end times helps a lot for effective closure

User Errors: We can reduce human error since program does the activity

Productivity: User productivity will be increased, so that user can focus on other activities

REFERENCES

[1]. Creating Auto Adjustments – Oracle Documentation https://docs.oracle.com/cd/E51111_01/current/html/ducset.html

[2]. Oracle ERP R12 Documentation https://docs.oracle.com/cd/E51111_01/current/html/ducset.html

[3]. Vinoth N <https://www.linkedin.com/in/vinoth-n-75223230>